

Effect of Covid-19 Pandemic on the Level of Death Anxiety of an Individual

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ABSTRACT

Background: Various people in the world currently struggling from COVID-19 ongoing pandemic. Despite the high prevalence, studies on COVID-19 and its effect on the mental health of the people, its effect on Death Anxiety study are lacking in our country. People are suffering from stress, anxiety, depression, due to COVID. Many people lost their loved ones and facing trauma due to their loss, they are being self-isolated, which increases fear of death among the individuals. The increasing of COVID-19 pandemic is most serious problem in present, Vaccines are approved and 70% people are vaccinated now but still many active cases are present in country. **Aim:** Study was to assess the impact of COVID on the level of Death Anxiety of the individual, Researcher conducted the study by doing comparative study between Post-COVID diagnosed individual and Non-diagnosed individual. **Methods:** In study, sample has selected to match the study and help in achieving the purpose of the study. The researcher used quota sampling for the data collection; Data were collected online by the help of Google form by the help of Ex post facto research design using quota-sampling method. A sample of 60, 30 Post-COVID diagnosed and 30 Non-Diagnosed individuals of age group 20 to 55 years was selected for present research with the help of Death Anxiety Scale constructed by Dr. Upinder Dhar, Dr.Savita Mehta, Dr. Santosh Dhar. **Statistical Techniques:** Data were analyzed with the help of t-test. The statistical analysis of the research study was carried out by comparing the Post-COVID diagnosed individual to Non-diagnosed individual. **Result:** The calculated t-value exceeds the critical value ($3.75 > 2.68$). By conventional criteria, this difference is considered to be statistically significant. Hence, null hypothesis is rejected. Thus result reveals that post-COVID diagnosed individual have greater death anxiety than individual who haven't been diagnosed with COVID. So it can be concluded that Post-COVID diagnosed individual are in constant fear of death because they have experienced it while the Non-diagnosed individual are safe so they don't have fear of death due to COVID. **Conclusion:** To summarize, the findings of the obtained quantitative data by the help of experimental research on the "Effect of COVID-19 on the level of Death Anxiety of an individual" researcher examined that Post-COVID Diagnosed individual have greater death anxiety than the individual who haven't diagnosed with COVID.

Keywords: COVID-19 Pandemic and Death Anxiety.

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INTRODUCTION

In December 2019, a novel Corona Virus was first detected in the city of Wuhan, China. Within five weeks, the virus, was named COVID-19, began to dominate global headlines. By mid-May 2020, COVID-19 had resulted in the deaths of uncountable people worldwide, with nearly 4.5 million cases confirmed Menzies & Menzies [1]. As cases increased, governments around the world began closing borders, and introducing social distancing restrictions and lockdown orders, in an effort to slow the rapid acceleration of the virus.

While a variety of restriction measures were employed by different countries, home isolation was one of the most common, Lockdown is understood as the restriction of movement with the aim to reduce the virus spread across a population. Side effects due to this drastic measure generates concern and anxiety in individuals.

Emerging research data are already revealing high levels of anxiety concerning the virus, with findings from nearly 5000 participants suggesting that greater perceived severity of the virus is associated with poorer mental health outcomes [2] but also Fears of death have been proposed to be a central and universal part of the experience of being human [3]. Death anxiety has been proposed to be a transdiagnostic construct, underpinning a range of different mental health conditions.

The recent COVID-19 pandemic has triggered a surge in anxiety across the globe. Much of the public's behavioural and emotional response to the virus can be understood through the framework of terror management theory, which proposes that fear of death drives much of human behaviour. In the context of the current pandemic, death anxiety, a recently proposed transdiagnostic construct, appears especially relevant. Fear of death has recently been shown to predict not only anxiety related to COVID-19, but also to play a causal role in various mental health conditions.

Death anxiety has been called the fear that people feel in the face of the end of their existence in this world [4]. People's perception of death is shaped according to the death events they see in their environment, like we all know due to crisis massive peoples death is reported in recent time, As it is known that people experienced conditions such as sickness, loneliness, anxiety, panic, stigma and death anxiety in previous epidemic period, it has been stated that individuals will be likely to experience similar problems in the COVID-19 epidemicso, it's obvious that it also has effect on the people's perception of death and it strongly impact mental health, especially among people who feel most anxious about the imminence of death.

Thus, This study is being conducted in order to check that COVID -19 has not only impact on death anxiety related to COVID, but it also has adverse effect on the death anxiety related to normal things happening in day-to-day life. These results contribute in the well-being of an individual during the Pandemic.

AIM & OBJECTIVES

1. To find the effect of COVID-19 on the level of death anxiety of an individual.
2. To find the difference in the level of death anxiety on COVID-19 Diagnosed and Non-diagnosed individual.

Hypothesis: In present research, researcher formulated the following null hypotheses for empirical verification.

1. There is no significant difference between the level of death anxiety of COVID-19 diagnosed and Non-diagnosed individuals.

Research Gap

Various study have done on Death Anxiety and COVID-19 relation, Loneliness perceived by elderly people during COVID-19, anxiety and depression related to COVID-19, But no study have conducted to do comparative study between Post-COVID diagnosed individual and non-diagnosed individual to check their level of Death Anxiety.

Therefore, the Researcher wants to check the effect of COVID-19on the level of Death Anxiety of an individual by comparing Post-COVID diagnosed individual and Non-diagnosed individual.

Description of Variables

For this research work researcher choose Death Anxiety as a dependent variable. The details of the variables concerned to this study are mentioned below:

Methods

The method of research provides tools and techniques by which the research problem is investigated thus the purpose of the research is to discover answer to the questions through the applications of scientific procedure. This chapter gives an outline of the methodology used in the study:

Inclusion Criteria

In this research, researchers have included subjects of age group 20 to 55 years of gender, Male as well as female. Subjects in this test are Post-COVID diagnosed Individual who are now well, their test is negative now and diagnosed with COVID 1 or 2 months ago and Non- COVID diagnosed individual who are safe with COVID.

Exclusion Criteria

In this research, Maximum people of 20 to 30 years are taken in this research, Elderly people is also excluded in this research who may be suffering from Death Anxiety due to their age and may be have fear of Death due to loss of their loved ones. Individual with chronic ailments like Cancer, Kidney failure, Diabetes, Blood pressure patients, etc. has been excluded because they might have fear of death due to their underlying disease.

Research Design

For the present research, researcher used ex-post facto design used or the data were analyzed and proper statistical techniques used.

Sample & Sampling

Samples of 60 participants between them 30 were Post-COVID. Diagnosed individual and 30 were Non-diagnosed individual. The data is collected between the age 20-55 year by the help of Google form, from different states. Researcher has used quota-sampling technique for the data collection.

Research Tool

Diagnosed individuals of age group 20 to 55 years was selected for present research with the help of Death Anxiety Scale constructed by Dhar, Mehta & Dhar S [5].

Data Collection Procedure

Firstly, Death Anxiety and COVID-19 pandemic were chosen as the variable. Research reviews were taken to understand the relation between the two variables. A questionnaire was selected i.e., Death Anxiety Scale Sample of 60 was selected using Quota sampling. The COVID-diagnosed individual and Non-diagnosed individual were selected for doing comparative study. The questionnaire was provided to them by the Google form medium for online data collection. After completion of data collection, Scoring of the questionnaires was done and the result was formulated with the help of t-test statistical analysis tools. After calculating t-test, level of confidence was checked and Interpretation and Discussion were done and Conclusion was given.

Statistical Techniques

In this research did a study over a variable i.e. Death Anxiety. The work is conducted on Post-COVID diagnosed individual and Non-COVID Diagnosed individual. Researcher used t-test for statistical analysis.

Result & Interpretation

Collected data through above-mentioned inventories were analyzed in terms of mean, standard deviation and t-test method. The results have been presented in the tables.

H₀: There is no significant effect of the COVID-19 on the level of death anxiety of an individual

H_a: There is significant effect of the COVID-19 on the level of death anxiety of an individual

Comparison the level of death anxiety between Post-COVID diagnosed Individual & Non-COVID Diagnosed Individual

Groups	N	Death Anxiety Scores		SE _D	t-value	Significance Level
		Mean	SD			
Post-COVID Diagnosed Individual	30	5.27	1.50	0.41	3.75	at 0.05 level
Non-COVID Diagnosed Individual	30	3.73	1.59			

$df = (n_1+n_2-2) = (30+30-2) = 58$

From the above result and graphical representation, it is interpreted that there is significant difference between the level of death anxiety of and Post-COVID diagnosed individual and Non-COVID diagnosed individual. The null hypothesis has been rejected at level of confidence and the alternate hypothesis has been accepted. The result indicates that Post- COVID diagnosed individual have more death anxiety than individual who has not been diagnosed with COVID.

This result shows that individual who has been diagnosed by COVID-19 in the past and are fine now they still have greater and high death anxiety than the individual who haven't diagnosed by COVID-19 yet, they have average or low level of Death Anxiety. Which means that Post-COVID diagnosed individual are in constant fear of death, not only by COVID-19 but by normal things also.

Its reason is clear that in life of Post-COVID diagnosed individual the fear of death remains because they faced the fear when they were COVID-positive where as in life of Normal individual the fear of death also remains normal because they know that one day they will die and they didn't faced the experience of COVID happening to them.

This research finding suggested that due to COVID-19 pandemic people are in tension and anxiety. Death anxiety appears to emerge as an abnormal experience when people face threats to mortality for reasons such as experiences or fear of COVID-19. The results of this study provide evidence that the COVID-19 pandemic causes more death anxiety, mostly in the people who have been diagnosed with it. In this case, they need to practice mindfulness, meditation, they need to calm down, they need to think positively that they recovered from COVID and yet they are still alive, so they do not need to fear for death and enjoy their life.

A study conducted on the fears of death in the context of the pandemic. The findings revealed a significant positive correlation between death anxiety and anxious beliefs and behaviours related to COVID-19 [6].

According to Silva, de Sampaio Brito, & Pereira [7] conducted a study on Brazilians participants 352, who answered a measurement of fear of death and read a news story about COVID-19. The results showed that individual differences in fear of death related to well-being, and that this relationship was mediated by anxiety in face of COVID-19.

A study conducted by Özgüç, Kaplan Serin, & Tanriverdi [8] on death anxiety associated with corona virus disease. The findings suggest that death anxiety was relatively high during the COVID-19 pandemic process.

Lee, Jobe, Mathis & Gibbons [9] conducted a research resulted that a series of hierarchical multiple regression analyses demonstrated that corona phobia explained additional variance in depression, generalized anxiety, and death anxiety, above sociodemographic, COVID-19 factors, and the vulnerability factors of neuroticism, health anxiety, and reassurance-seeking behaviors.

Study was conducted by Alenazi et al., [10] to explored the anxiety levels among HCWs in Saudi Arabia during the COVID-19 pandemic and the predictors of increased anxiety levels. Participants reporting high anxiety levels were more likely to be unmarried, nurses, workers in radiology or respiratory therapists.

The research conducted by Karabağ Aydın & Fidan [11] on the effect of nurses' death anxiety on life satisfaction during the COVID-19 pandemic. Study resulted that death anxiety adversely affects life satisfaction. Higher death anxiety among nurses was associated with lower satisfaction with life.

Many Findings and researched revealed the effect of COVID-19. Therefore, it is obvious that COVID-19 have effect on Peoples mental health and increasing death anxiety. However, more in the Post-COVID diagnosed people because they suffer from it and experienced it in compare to Non-COVID diagnosed individual.

CONCLUSION

The main aim of the study is to reveal whether there is an effect of COVID-19 on the level of death anxiety of an individuals. The research study includes the comparison of post-COVID diagnosed individual and Non-COVID diagnosed individual. The sample included 30 Post-COVID diagnosed individuals and 30 Non-COVID diagnosed individual.

After the data collection, analysis was done with the help of t-test and result were formulated which shows that the COVID-19 pandemic do affect the level of death anxiety of an individuals who was diagnosed by COVID-19 and are recovered in comparison with the individuals who are not diagnosed with COVID yet.

From the above study, it is concluded that this pandemic have greater impact of fear and anxiety related to death on the individuals not only by COVID but it also have impacted on day to day life things.

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